

COPE-KNOEVENAGEL REACTION DYNAMICS. PART II. THE ROLE OF ACETIC ACID AS THE IONISING MEDIUM

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In a condensation reaction of levulinic ester with cyanoacetic ester, the proportions of ammonium acetate and acetic acid have been varied. It is concluded that the function of acetic acid is limited not exclusively to a simple ionisation.

It has been mentioned in the preceding part (*this Journal*, 1953, 30, 205) that acetic acid serves as the ionising medium and benzene is the best solvent for removal of water. Perhaps the function of the acetic acid is limited not only to a simple ionisation but something more which will be clear from the results obtained in the present investigation.

The results in Tables I to IV refer to the yields of the product of condensation of levulinic ester with cyanoacetic ester in presence of varying proportions of ammonium acetate, the catalyst and acetic acid. In all the experiments the proportions of the reactants, except the catalyst and acetic acid, and the conditions are as described in the Experimental.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Equimolar amounts (0.1 *M*) of levulinic ester and cyanoacetic ester together with ammonium acetate and acetic acid in benzene (75 c.c.) were refluxed for 3 hours with varying amounts of the acid or the catalyst in the apparatus described previously (*loc. cit.*) to remove the water continuously as formed. The time was kept constant whether the reaction came to an end or not. Table I records the yield with varying quantities of acetic acid, keeping that of ammonium acetate constant at 0.025*M*. It will be seen that corresponding to 0.075-0.1 *M*, the yield is maximum. On either side of the maximum unchanged materials were recovered.

TABLE I

Acetic acid (<i>M</i>)	0	0.025	0.05	0.075	0.1	0.2	0.4
Yield (g.)	9.5	11.5	14.8	17.0	17.5	14.0	11.5

The yield data in a similar series of experiments in which the acetic acid was fixed at 0.1*M* and the proportion of ammonium acetate was varied from 0.025 to 0.4 *M* are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Am. acetate (<i>M</i>)	0.0	0.025	0.05	0.1	0.2	0.4
Yield (g.)	0.0	17.18	15.5	14.4	13.3	9.8

The lower yield on either side of the maximum, however, is found unlike the preceding case to be due to the formation of high boiling or even solid byproducts.

A higher proportion of acetic acid generally favours a large yield as the data in Table III show. Of course, it should be admitted that with a variation of acid concentration there is some variation also of the catalytic constant (Bell and Lidwell, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 1096).

TABLE III

	Acetic acid.	Am. acetate.	Yield.
Case I	0.1 M	0.025M	17.7 g.
	0.025	0.1	14.0
Case II	0.15	0.05	17.0
	0.05	0.15	13.5

But it is not only the proportion of the two, but the absolute quantities of the catalyst and the acetic acid are also to be taken into consideration to ensure higher yield. For instance, the results in Table IV were obtained with a constant proportion of the acid to the catalyst, but their net concentrations were gradually increased. The proportion corresponding to 0.1M Am. acetate and 0.15 M acetic acid appears to provide the maximum yield. However, all proportions were not tried and, hence, the optimum combination of the acid and the catalyst could not be obtained.

TABLE IV

Am. acetate (M)	...	0.025	0.050	0.075	0.1	0.2
Acetic acid (M)	...	0.0375	0.075	0.113	0.15	0.3
Yield (g.)	...	6.8	15.4	16.0	16.6	11.0

It is known that elimination of water at the last stage is catalysed by acid. That is possibly the reason why a larger quantity of acid ensures a higher yield.

Two other catalysts besides ammonium acetate were tried in another series of experiments, in which 0.1M acetic acid was used. The proportion of the remaining reactants and the experimental conditions were the same as before. It will be clear from Table V that ammonium acetate is undoubtedly the best catalyst studied so far.

TABLE V

Catalyst.	Yield.
0.025 M acetamide	1 g.
„ piperazine diacetate	12
„ Am. acetate	11.5

is a reversible one (Wittig and Hartmann, *Ber.*, 1939, 72, 1387; Cope *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 3452) and should consequently be catalysed by acetate ion.

Brønsted (*Chem. Rev.*, 1928, 49, 2327) is of the opinion that almost all acid-base catalysed reactions take place through the preliminary formation of a critical complex which acts as a very reactive intermediate. Such an idea was also envisaged by Watson (*Ann. Rept. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 38, 214; cf. Bell and Caldin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 38a) for the Knoevenagel reaction. The formation of a critical complex is also supported by our experiments with different solvents described earlier (Raha, *loc. cit.*). There, it has been found that with donor solvents like Ac_2O , thioether etc., the unchanged materials are received back.